

Queenship and Cross-Confessional Identity

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Abstract: This cluster focuses on the cross-confessional nature of European queenship, particularly the role that different confessional identities play in the education, marriage, childbirth, patronage, expressions of agency, legal context, and posthumous legacy of queens, both regnant and consort. Ranging from the education of Isabella I’s daughters to Catholic consorts in the Stuart realms to posthumous understandings of Anne Boleyn, this cluster features the work of both emerging and established scholars, all of whom seek to contribute to the field of royal studies’ engagement with queens’ religion across confessional lines, including intra-Christian relations and the interplay between the Christian, Jewish, and Muslim faiths. After a brief introduction to the conceptual framework of the cluster, eight discrete short-form articles examine different aspects of European queenship and their cross-confessional identities.

Key Words: Confessionalism, Confessional Identity, Catholicism, Protestantism, Queenship, Education, Patronage, Legacy

Introductory Notes

Amy Saunders and Johanna C.E. Strong

INDEPENDENT SCHOLARS

This cluster explores queenship and cross-confessional identities, bringing together works on a variety of European queens including Mary I, Anne Boleyn, Catherine of Braganza, and Mary of Modena.¹ Ranging from education to marriage to memory, these present discussions all centre on an understanding of confessionalism as being “the ‘outward’ expression of religious faith and

¹ The editors also extend their thanks to Ellie Woodacre for her ongoing encouragement, and support, to the contributors for their hard work and fascinating scholarship, and to the peer reviewers for their valuable insights.

the belief that politics and society should be bound by certain aspects of this faith.”² Consequently, when queens held a religious belief distinct from that of their realm they existed in a cross-confessional environment, “where their own religious identity was in direct conflict to the official religious identity of their husbands and subjects.”³ This cluster uses this definition of confessionalism and cross-confessionalism to better understand the religious environments of the various queens regnant and consort examined here and to extend traditional understandings of this aspect of the royal studies field.

Discussions of cross-confessional monarchical identity tend to be confined to examinations of the medieval and early modern periods and examinations particularly of Protestant-Catholic marriage and identity before the eighteenth century.⁴ This cluster, however, addresses these oversights by situating these wider discussions within the traditional framework of understandings of cross-confessional identity in early modern Europe. This cluster moves beyond the traditional Protestant-Catholic boundary through Melania Soler Moratón’s discussion of the education of Isabella I of Castile’s daughters and the influence of Castile’s multi-faith context. This cluster also extends its examination beyond the traditional chronological ending point of the seventeenth century, particularly through Sarah Betts’s work. Betts bases her examination of the cross-confessional elements of the Act of Settlement and the changes it wrought to British monarchy on understandings of early modern Protestant-Catholic cross-confessionalisation but broadens this conversation to include a shifting political atmosphere in the eighteenth century.

This collection of articles brings together a unique range of queens regnant and consort to explore how these women navigated their individual cross-confessional environments. It demonstrates the various ways in which they pursued their own confessional interests and how these activities crossed international borders. This cluster therefore contributes to the growing field of queenship studies, with themes of agency,

² Amy Saunders, “Construction, Deconstruction, and Reconstruction: Stuart Kings and Queens in Heritage Sites” (Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Winchester, 2024), 15.

³ Saunders, “Construction, Deconstruction, and Reconstruction,” 15.

⁴ For cross-confessional identities, see, for example: Adam Morton and Nadine Lewycky, ed., *Getting Along? Religious Identities and Confessional Relations in Early Modern England: Essays in Honour of Professor W. J. Sheils* (London and New York: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, 2012); and Marc R. Forster and Benjamin J. Kaplan, ed., *Piety and Family in Early Modern Europe: Essays in Honour of Steven Ozment* (London and New York: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, 2005). For royal cross-confessional identities, see, for example: Valentina Caldari and Sara J. Wolfson, ed., *Stuart Marriage Diplomacy: Dynastic Politics in their European Context, 1604–1630* (Woodbridge: The Boydell Press, 2018); Johanna C. E. Strong, “The Making of a Queen: The Effect of Religion, National Identity, and Gender on Mary I’s Legacy in the English Historical Narrative” (Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Winchester, 2022).

Article: "Queenship and Cross-Confessional Identity"

patronage, self-fashioning, and networking at its core. By moving beyond traditional chronological and confessional boundaries it also suggests future avenues of research that many of the authors included intend to pursue further.

Henrietta Maria’s French Mediation as English Queen²⁶

Mercedes Llorente

UNIVERSITAT JAUME I

In undertaking research on Catherine of Bragança, queen consort to Charles II, I discovered that a portrait of her father hung in Henrietta Maria’s chapel at Somerset House. This paper focuses on Henrietta Maria, consort of Charles I, and takes as its starting point the history of diplomacy, female agency, and political negotiation of this Catholic queen of the Stuart court. As some scholars of the queen, such as Erin Griffey, point out, in her portraits and the artwork in her palaces and chapels Henrietta Maria placed herself within a discourse, between the expectations of her husband Charles I, her family in France, her religious entourages, the papacy, her own personal devotions, and the public in a predominantly Protestant country.²⁷ Part of this discourse was Henrietta Maria’s mediation as queen of England, particularly the role of her understanding of piety, as displayed in her Somerset House chapel through its decorative programme and the art she exhibited there.

This article also analyses the different forms of political and cultural mediation which Henrietta Maria put into practice as princess of France and Queen of England. Finally, it will explore how Henrietta Maria used the portrait of João IV of Portugal in her chapel, both as an instrument of agency and as “mute mediation,” as Anthony Calantuano has defined some works of art used during diplomatic negotiations intended to send a specific message, based on shared codes of visual communication, in this case from the court of London.²⁸

Opening up new formulas for cross-cultural studies, it will be seen that investigating the material culture of agency implies the need to study a complex web of relationships between material objects, human beings, and interior and exterior spaces in order to uncover the political, social, and legal significance of the ways in which political actors brought

²⁶ María Zambrano Postdoctoral contract MAZ/2022/2024 (UP2021-021) financed by the European Union – NextGenerationEU. This article is part of my research on Henrietta Maria’s daughter-in-law, Catherine Braganza, which I was able to carry out thanks to a grant awarded to me by the Warburg Institute (2020).

²⁷ Erin Griffey, *On Display: Henrietta Maria and the Materials of Magnificence at the Stuart Court* (London and New Haven: The Paul Mellon Centre for Studies on British Art & Yale University, 2015).

²⁸ Anthony Colantuano, “The Mute Diplomat: Theorizing the Role of Images in Seventeenth-Century Political Negotiations,” in *The Diplomacy of Art: Artistic Creation and Politics in Seicento Italy*, ed. Elizabeth Cropper (Milan: Electa, 2000), 54; Nancy Um and Leah R. Clark, “Introduction. The Art of Embassy: Situating Objects and Images in the Early Modern diplomatic Encounter,” *Journal of Early Modern History* 20 (2016): 1.

artefacts into play during negotiation, as Harriet Rudolph has pointed out in the article “Entangled Objects.”²⁹

The Historical Background of Henrietta Maria

Henrietta Maria, princess of France, was born on 25 November 1609, St. Catherine’s Day. She was the youngest daughter of Henri IV of France and Marie de Medici and was named after both her parents. The education of the princess was under the supervision of her mother and the letters of Queen Marie de Medici show us how she instructed her daughter to be an agent for the interests of her French family. These letters from Queen Marie to her daughter Henrietta Maria depart from the rhetoric that defines virtuous women as docile, silent, and under male supervision and care, revealing a constant negotiation between domesticity and the effective power that Marie demanded of her. As a daughter of France, Henrietta Maria had specific duties to fulfil. Within marriage, a woman was supposed to ensure that her husband was favourably disposed towards her relatives, which—in her role as queen of England—meant working for French interests, too.³⁰

After the marriage contract was signed, Charles I became king following the death of his father James VI & I (d. 27 March 1625) and married Henrietta Maria of France by proxy in May in Paris; in this manner it was publicly demonstrated that a new alliance had been forged between the Stuart and Bourbon dynasties. Henrietta Maria set off with her French household to new territories and began her tenure as a Stuart queen consort. Many, including the English Parliament itself, greeted her marriage with outright hostility, opposing a French Catholic princess because of fears that Charles would lift restrictions on Catholics and undermine Protestantism. Indeed, Henrietta Maria exercised influence over the affections and judgement of the king, as was expected in her role as wife and queen consort, which Protestants interpreted as a confirmation of their fears.

Although Charles I was tolerant towards Catholics, Parliament’s policies attempted to have control over them—especially over those who met in the various embassy chapels. Catholic embassies with chapels, such as those of Venice, Spain, France, and Portugal,

²⁹ Harriet Rudolph, “Entangled Objects and Hybrid Practices? Material Culture as a New Approach to the History of Diplomacy,” in *Material Culture in Modern Diplomacy from the 15th to the 20th Century*, ed. Harriet Rudolph and Gregor M. Metzger (Berlin and Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2016), 13.

³⁰ Anne J. Cruz and Nieves Baranda Leturio, ed., *Routledge Research Companion to Early Modern Spanish Women Writers* (New York: Routledge, 2017); Erin Griffey, “Picturing Confessional Politics at the Stuart Court: Henrietta Maria and Catherine of Braganza,” *Journal of Religious History* 44 (November 2020): 465–493.

continued to hold masses and welcome English Catholics, but Parliament opposed them. It is in this context that the queen must be placed.

Henrietta Maria was involved in English politics and effectively played an important role as a Catholic queen. As the country headed hopelessly towards open conflict in the 1630s, in the middle of that same decade the queen had positioned herself at the centre of confessional politics; the opening of her chapel at Somerset House, the introduction of papal envoys, and the conversion of many at court to Catholicism made her unpopular. Later, Parliament accused the queen of high treason, and she was exiled to France in 1644 and later to Holland. After the execution of her husband, Charles I, in 1649, the dowager queen worked to help their son return to the throne and supported his marriage to the *Infanta* Catherine of Bragança (1638–1705), daughter of the new Portuguese King João IV (1604–1656). As queen mother, Henrietta Maria returned to London after her son was crowned in 1660 and lived there until 1664, when, for medical reasons, she had to return to Paris, where she died in 1669.

A Catholic Queen's Piety in a Protestant Court

When Henrietta Maria and her French entourage arrived at the English court in 1625, she was given rooms in the King's principal palaces, St James's, Whitehall, and Hampton Court, but as queen consort she had her own household and received six palaces as part of her marriage treaty and she was permitted the free exercise of Roman Catholic religion in the palaces or royal houses in which she lived, where she could have a chapel or another place to pray.³¹ The queen spent more time in her palaces and focused on decorating them in her own style. She moved from one palace to another to celebrate feasts or to attend masses and other religious services in her various chapels. Capuchin and Franciscan priests and monks attended these Catholic chapels in her palaces, which had been established for Henrietta Maria's own devotions and those of her ladies, the rest of the Catholic courtiers, and, at certain times of the year, the public more broadly.

Henrietta Maria's most important place of power and influence was Somerset House, where she held court. Major renovations to the private and public rooms of this palace began

³¹ Joan-Luis Palos and Magdalena S. Sanchez, ed., *Early Modern Dynastic Marriages and Cultural Transfer* (London: Routledge, 2016); Erin Griffey, "The Materials of Marital Diplomacy: Henrietta Maria's Trousseau," in *The Age of Rubens: Diplomacy, Dynastic Politics and the Visual Arts in Early Seventeenth-century Europe*, ed. Robert Malcolm Smuts and Luc Duerloo (Turnhout: Brepol, 2016), 197.

in 1628, and it was here that she spent most of her time. Henrietta Maria designed the space culturally and politically to be a centre of Catholic and French style and religiosity.

Henrietta Maria also commissioned the construction of a new, separate chapel at Somerset House designed by Inigo Jones. The chapel is dedicated to the Virgin Mary, to whom she felt a close affinity due to their shared name and the expectations of motherhood placed upon her.³² Building continued from 1630 (when she gave birth to Charles, Prince of Wales on 29 May) until 1636 (after having Mary in 1631, James in 1633, and Elizabeth in 1635) and the chapel was formally opened on 1 July, although the first mass took place on 10 December. Reconstruction of the chapel’s architecture is complicated by the few surviving designs by Jones. However, historian Simon Thurley provides a useful overview, showing how the Superior of the Capuchins and the queen herself played an active role in the design, and how the Counter-Reformation and Jesuit churches influenced them.³³ Strategic gifts of pictures, relics, and holy books also demonstrated the influence and the presence of papal agents.³⁴

The queen’s accounts provide information about the use of rich materials in the interior of the chapel. An example is the expenditure on textiles such as embroidery, lace, damasks, and velvets for the vestments and liturgical cloths of different colours to accommodate the religious calendar, as shown in the chapel inventories.³⁵ This article will focus more on the pictorial decoration of Somerset Chapel. In 1649–1651 a list of the “Somerset House Chapel paintings” was drawn up as part of the Commonwealth sales, which included forty-one paintings, the majority of which—twenty-seven—were religious.³⁶

The ceiling was decorated with a painting by William Goodricke and Thomas de Critz depicting the *Assumption of the Virgin*. On the altar was the painting of the *Crucifixion* by Peter Paul Rubens which had been a gift from the King to his wife. Both were destroyed in the iconoclastic attacks on the chapel on 30 and 31 March 1643. The chapel was the centre where Catholics were attended and listened to, and also the centre of accusations of papism.

The most popular subject in the Somerset House chapel was the Virgin Mary with Child, appearing in six of the thirteen paintings with this theme; in others she was portrayed

³² Griffey, *On Display*; Oliver Millar, ed., *The Forty-Third Volume of The Walpole Society 1970–1972: The Inventories and Valuations of The King’s Goods 1649–1651* (Glasgow: University Press Glasgow, 1972), 413–414.

³³ Simon Thurley, *Whitehall Palace: An Architectural of the Royal Apartments, 1240–1698* (New Haven and London: Yale University Press in association with Historic Royal Palaces 1999), 116.

³⁴ Panzani in 1634 and George Conn in 1636, among others.

³⁵ Millar, *The Forty-Third Volume*, 407–413.

³⁶ Millar, *The Forty-Third Volume*, 413–416.

with significant figures such as St. Joseph (*Holy Family*), St. John the Baptist, and the Wise Men among others, or alone as in the *Salutation*. Of all the possible themes of the Virgin Mary, Henrietta Maria chose images of the Virgin Mary as the mother of Jesus, perhaps to reflect her own motherhood, having recently given birth to four children, the first of whom was the heir to the throne, Charles. It was the queen, as Erica Veevers has shown, who introduced the Cult of the Virgin to the court in the 1630s.³⁷ Many chapels of queens and women dedicated to the Virgin Mary were closely related to Mary's maternity and their own maternity, an important and fearful moment for women at a time when many of them died in childbirth.³⁸ What is known is that Henrietta Maria gave birth to her first five children in the rooms of the king's palace at St James's; this chapel therefore might be closely related not to the rituals of birth but to Mary as mother. The Virgin Mary was the most important model of virtue for women in general, even more so for a Catholic queen, for whom there could be no more powerful intercessor. And, as mentioned before, the chapel was dedicated to the Virgin Mary which was the name of the queen as well.

It should be pointed out that Mary has an important place in post-Reformation England because of what she reveals about Christ, her son. But the Reformers could not accept that Mary had an intercessory role in any way. In addition, the Church of England viewed images as a key component of their fight against Catholicism because images symbolised all the external and ceremonial aspects that had to be reformed. Although, as discussed above, the queen was allowed the free exercise of the Roman Catholic religion in the palaces or royal houses in which she lived, in so doing she distanced herself from her subjects.

The Commonwealth inventory shows other records, too, such as five images of Mary Magdalene. Many elite women felt a great affinity with this saint, because of her virtues, her links to luxury, the ascetic piety she represents, and because of her active role in religious life. Mary Magdalene was chosen to find Christ at his Resurrection and it was she who told the Apostles. As such, Mary Magdalene was a model for women who also wanted to have an active role in religious life, be recognised for their faith, and be figures in public life. Marie

³⁷ Erica Veevers, *Images of Love and Religion: Queen Henrietta Maria and Court Entertainments* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1989).

³⁸ It is unknown whether these paintings of the Virgin with her son are associated with motherhood and related religious rituals and ceremonies during pregnancy, labour, and during recovery after childbirth, as for example, in the chapel of the Alcázar in Madrid with queen Isabel of Bourbon (1602–1644), Henrietta Maria's sister. See: María Cruz de Carlos Varona, *Nacer en palacio: El ritual del nacimiento en la corte de los Austrias* (Madrid: CEEH, 2018).

de Medici and Anne of Austria followed this cult in France, which confirms that the queen brought a certain French feminine spirituality to the court in London, a set of beliefs which had the support of Urban VIII, who also venerated Saint Mary Magdalene and expressly requested that her remains, buried in Provence, sanctify his splendid family chapel.³⁹ Other images made reference to power, such as *The Mockery of Christ*, with connotations for a royal audience. The queen’s loyalty to the papacy is also highlighted in a portrait of Pope Urban VIII, her godfather, and another painting of St. Peter with his keys.

Finally, three portraits are cited in the Commonwealth sale inventories: Henrietta Maria’s sister Christine, her brother Gaston, and João IV, King of Portugal, (father of the future Queen Catherine of Bragança, wife of Charles II).⁴⁰ In 1640, the Portuguese proclaimed the Duke of Bragança king, as João IV (1604–1656), and the separation of the Spanish and Portuguese monarchies materialised, thus starting a long war (from 1640 to 1668). It was in 1641 when the Bragança dynasty sent its first embassies carrying portraits to various European monarchies and republics to pursue its political objectives and gain their favour.⁴¹

Portraits were exchanged as gifts between the representatives of the different monarchies and were, in fact, important in specific historical situations, as was the case of the Bragança dynasty during the last decades of the seventeenth century. The new Bragança dynasty was attempting to gain recognition from other monarchies and one of its fundamental objectives was the recognition of Rome. To this end, the new king deployed mediation with Rome, but this was not achieved until Pedro II (1648–1706) came to the throne and his sister Catherine of Bragança became the wife of Charles II (1661). The portrait plays an essential role in the process of institutionalisation of the Portuguese dynasty and in its future relations with the rest of Europe. The court of the Stuarts received the Portuguese embassy of 1641 and with it came the portraits of the Braganças. Thanks to the inventories of the sale, it is possible at least to know where the portrait of the Portuguese king was placed and how it was used. It is not known, however, which of the portraits of the king was sent to

³⁹ Peter Rietbergen, *Power and Religion in Baroque Rome: Barberini Cultural Policies* (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2006), 385.

⁴⁰ Millar, *The Forty-Third Volume*, 415; Anne J Cruz, *Symbolic and Material Circulation between Spain and England, 1554–1604* (Aldershot, UK & Burlington, Vermont: Ashgate Press, 2008).

⁴¹ Pedro Cardim, “Embaixadores e representantes diplomáticos da coroa portuguesa no século XVII,” *Cultura 15* (2002); Pedro Cardim, “A prática diplomática na Europa do Antigo Regime,” in *Histia e Relações Internacionais: Temas e Debates*, ed. Luis Nino Rodrigues and Fernando Martins (Evora: Publicações do Cidehus, 2004); Pedro Cardim, “‘Nem tudo se pode escrever’: Correspondencia diplomática e información ‘política’ en Portugal durante el siglo XVII,” *Cuadernos de Historia Moderna, Anejos IV* (2005): 95–128.

the court of Charles I; nor do we know the name of the Portuguese painter or the date it was painted (before 1641), as the inventory only says Portuguese king.⁴²

The queen’s intention to support the Bragança dynasty was quite obvious, but the question remains: why was the portrait of King João IV displayed next to the French prince and princess? It is important to remember here that France and Portugal signed a first agreement on 1 June 1641, obliging each other to maintain war against Spain in order to weaken the Habsburgs. Later, the marriage negotiations between Portugal and France were organised. From very early on, the first children of the new dynasty—Theodosius (1634–1653), Joanna (1635–1653), and Catherine—played strategic roles in political alliances in the European context (mainly with Savoy and France). The marriages of the prince Theodosius Bragança to the eldest daughter of Gaston of Orléans (Queen Henrietta Maria’s brother), and of the Infanta Joanna Bragança to Christine’s son (Queen Henrietta Maria’s sister) were under discussion. These portraits of the siblings of the queen and the Portuguese king are therefore better understood in this context of negotiation.

The presentation of the three portraits staged Henrietta Maria’s support for the Portuguese, at a time when the Bragança monarchy had not yet been recognised by the Pope, which was not achieved until the reign of Pedro II (1648–1706), João’s second successor as king of Portugal. Therefore, the fact that the chapel at Somerset House contained these three portraits of the Portuguese king, and Henrietta Maria’s brother and sister, with one of the Pope not far from them, sent a clear message from the queen to all the Catholics who congregated there. They were also essential to show the political importance of the queen and her positioning as a liaison between the French, Stuart, and Portuguese courts in a Catholic chapel. Using them as a mute instrument in this context of war showed Henrietta Maria as a mediator of her French family as well, as Anthony Calantuano has defined for some works of art used during diplomatic negotiations intended to send a specific message, based on shared codes of visual communication.⁴³ The rhetorical conceptions deployed recognised Portugal as a monarchy and demonstrated the support of both the English and French monarchies for the Portuguese, showing a new political alliance on display in her chapel.

⁴² Pedro Cardim, “*Portugal unido y separado*. Propaganda y discurso identitario entre Austrias y Braganças,” *Espacio, Tiempo y Forma* 37, Serie IV, Historia Moderna, t. 25 (2012): 37–55; Pedro Flor, “*A arte do retrato em Portugal nos séculos xv e xvi, problemas, metodologia, linhas de investigação*,” *Revista de historia da arte* 5 (2008): 115–131; José Texeira, *A Iconografia da época da Restauração* (Évora: Museo de Évora, 1990); Victo Serrao, *A pintura Protobarroca em Portugal 1612–1657: O triunfo do naturalismo e do tenebrismo* (Lisbon: Edições Colibri, 2000); Luis de Moura Sobral, *Pintura Portuguesa do Século XVII, historias lendas narrativas* (Lisbon: Livraria Sá da Costa, Museo Nacional Arte Antiga, 2004).

⁴³ Calantuano, “The Mute Diplomat: Theorizing,” 54.

Images are complex inter-communicators that function both positively and negatively because of the different meanings they can suggest to their donors and their recipients, as in this case of the portrait of King João IV. These images bring other meanings to the negotiations and mediations between courts, with the patronage of women, particularly the queen, Henrietta Maria, across cultural and religious boundaries.

Henrietta Maria showed her political and religious position as Catholic queen consort of the Stuarts, but also as princess of France and ally of Portugal. In the middle of the negotiations, she defended Franco-Portuguese relations from the London court against the Catholic Monarchy in the most important Catholic chapel in London.

Figure 1. Unknown, *Portrait of King João IV*, C. 1641, no inv. PT/TT/ (Portugal).